

Local Government in South Africa

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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with the support of SALGA - South African Local Government Association

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments

5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in South Africa: An Introduction

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The Intergovernmental Relations Framework Act (IGRFA) establishes lines of communication and provides the institutional framework for interaction between national, provincial, and local spheres of government and all other organs of state.¹²⁴ The IGRFA aims to provide certainty, coherence, transparency and stability and to facilitate effective and coherent developmental outcomes as envisaged by the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996. Section 40(1) describes the three spheres of government as ‘distinctive, interdependent and interrelated’. Each sphere has autonomy to make final decisions within its areas of competence and there is a two-way relationship of regulation and oversight in order to be a coherent government.¹²⁵ The two main approaches to IGR are supervision and cooperation (Sections 100 and 139 of the Constitution).

Supervision

Section 151(3) of the Constitution stipulates that ‘a municipality has a right to govern, on its own initiative, the local government affairs of its community, subject to national and provincial legislation’. Further, Section 156 (1) grants exclusive legislative and executive authority to pass by-laws and administer local government matters listed in Schedules 4B and 5B, and any matters assigned by national or provincial government. However, National and provincial governments have legislative and executive authority to ensure that local governments perform their functions effectively in relation to matters listed in Schedules 4 and 5 (Sections 156(1) and 155(7) of the Constitution). This includes first, the power to ‘regulate’, which in the context of local government was interpreted by the Constitutional Court in the *Habitat* as follows: ‘It follows that “regulating” in Section 155(7) means creating norms and guidelines for the exercise of a power or the performance of a function. It does not mean the usurpation of the power or the performance of the function itself. This is because the power of regulation is afforded to national and provincial government in order “to see to the effective performance by municipalities of their functions”. The constitutional scheme does not envisage the province employing appellate power over municipalities’ exercise of their planning functions. This is so

¹²⁴ Act 13 of 2005.

¹²⁵ Nico Steytler, Yonatan Fessha and Coel Kirkby, ‘Status Quo Report on Intergovernmental Relations Regarding Local Government’ (Community Law Center CAGE Project, now Dullah Omar Institute 2006) <<https://dullahomarinate.org.za/multilevel-govt/publications/status-quo-report-on-provincial-local-igr.pdf>> accessed 30 July 2019.

even where the zoning, subdivision or land-use permission has province-wide implications.¹²⁶ Secondly, the national and provincial governments ‘monitor’ municipalities, which includes promoting the development of local capacity in order for local governments to perform their functions and to manage their affairs (Section 155(6)(a) of the Constitution).¹²⁷ Thirdly, national and provincial governments have powers to ‘intervene’ in municipalities that fail to fulfil their constitutional or legislative obligations. There are four types of interventions: regular, discretionary ‘serious financial problems’, mandatory budgetary interventions, and mandatory ‘financial crisis’ interventions (Section 139 of the Constitution). The Municipal Systems Act (MSA) and Municipal Finance Management Act (MFMA) contain further provisions pertaining to the monitoring powers of provincial and national government over local government.¹²⁸

Cooperation

Chapter 3 of the Constitution sets out general values and principles for cooperation such as mutual trust and good faith (Section 41 (1)(h)). All three spheres are required to build friendly relations, assist and support each other, coordinate actions and legislation, adhere to procedures, avoid legal proceedings against each other, and inform and consult each other on matters of common interest (Section 41(1)(h) of the Constitution). IGRFA established IGR forums and institutions that facilitate the realisation of these normative principles, for example, through compulsory IGR procedures such as the Division of Revenue Act which must go through each sphere of government (through participatory processes for local government, and legislative processes for provincial and national government) before it becomes law. Although Section 4 IGRFA stipulates that the objects of the act are to create a coherent government, the act focuses on IGR structures as opposed to principles; hierarchies are embedded in some of the IGR structures and national government is dominant in steering IGR, making IGR an object of the centre, and not a collaboration of equal partners.¹²⁹ Further, the principles are normative, and in certain instances, such as in *Ngwathe Local Municipality v Eskom Holdings SoC Ltd and Others*,¹³⁰ perceived failure to implement the principles of cooperation may lead to litigation. In this case, the local Municipality of Ngwathe failed to pay its electricity bill to Eskom, and when Eskom threatened to disconnect the electricity supply, Ngwathe local municipality instituted legal action on the basis that Eskom, as an organ of state,

¹²⁶ Nico Steytler and Jaap de Visser, *Local Government Law of South Africa* (LexisNexis 2018) 5-24 (12A); *Minister of Local Government, Environmental Affairs and Development Planning, Western Cape v The Habitat Council and Others*; *Minister of Local Government, Environmental Affairs and Development Planning, Western Cape v City of Cape Town and Others* 2014 (5) BCLR 591 (CC) (Habitat CC) [22].

¹²⁷ See also Secs 105 and 106 of the Municipal Systems Act (MSA) 32 of 2000.

¹²⁸ MSA Act 32 of 2000; Municipal Finance Management Act (MFMA) 56 of 2003.

¹²⁹ Nico Steytler; 'Cooperative and Coercive Models of Intergovernmental Relations: A South African Case Study' in Thomas J Courchene and others (eds), *The Federal Idea: Essays in Honour of Ronald L. Watts* (1 ed, Queen's School of Policy Studies 2011).

¹³⁰ [2015] ZAFSHC 104 (28 May 2015).

had a legal obligation to respect the functional or institutional integrity of Ngwathe local municipality.

Intergovernmental Forums and Institutions

The IGRFA creates intergovernmental forums, where executives of the three spheres of government meet (Section 41(2) of the Constitution). Deemed as the main coordinating body at national level, the President's Coordinating Council (PCC) consists of the President, the Deputy President, relevant Ministers in the Presidency, Finance and Public Service respectively, Premiers from each of the nine provinces and a municipal councillor designated by SALGA. The PCC is a consultative forum for the President to raise matters of national interest with provinces and organised local government, to consult them on the implementation of national policy, co-ordination and alignment of priorities, and to discuss strategic priorities inter alia. Because the PCC is hierarchical, it tends to be a forum for the President to tell provinces and municipalities what to do, and to detect failures by provinces and municipalities. This leaves very little room for SALGA to make substantial contributions, and if it does, it is difficult to see these translated into policy reform as the agenda is set by the President in terms of Section 8(1)b IGRFA. However, proposals for the agenda can be submitted to the Minister in the Presidency. The IGRFA requires only one member of SALGA to be in attendance- the municipal councillor. The municipal councillor is selected from among SALGA members (as SALGA is organised local government and represents all municipalities in South Africa). The IGRFA does not specify the frequency of meetings of the PCC, but it simply requires that the PCC meets, at the behest of the President of the Republic (Section 8(1)(a)), to oversee and ensure alignment between the spheres and implementation of national policies and legislation.

Further, each national department has a national IGR forum where Ministers meet with Members of the (Provincial) Executive (MinMECs) and a national councillor from SALGA, provided the subject matter of the specific MinMec deals with a matter assigned to local governments in terms of Schedule 4B or 5B. Section 18 IGRFA stipulates that MinMECs are a consultative forum 'for' the relevant cabinet member to facilitate alignment between the national and provincial spheres on topical or sectoral issues. MinMECs are hierarchical and can become 'instruments of centralised control' and 'vehicles of command'.¹³¹ There is also a variation called the Local Government Ministerial and Member of the (provincial) Executive forum (LGMinMEC), which invites local government into joint sessions with the provincial and national executive.¹³² The reports of the MinMEC must be submitted to the President's Coordinating Council. In this way, issues raised by provincial MEC and SALGA will be presented to the President through the PCC.

¹³¹ Nico Steytler, 'National Cohesion and Intergovernmental Relations in South Africa' in Nico Steytler and Yash Pal-Ghai (eds), *Kenyan-South African Dialogue on Devolution* (Juta 2016) 313.

¹³² Derek Powell, 'Constructing a Developmental State in South Africa: The Corporatisation of Intergovernmental Relations' in Johanne Poirier, Cheryl Saunders and John Kincaid (eds), *Intergovernmental Relations in Federal Systems* (Oxford University Press 2015) 327.

The Premier's IGR Forum (PIF) is a horizontal forum for the Premier and mayors of district and metropolitan municipalities. The PIF comprises of the Premier of a specific province, provincial cabinet members, mayors of metropolitan and district municipalities, and a representative of SALGA. Unlike the PCC and MinMECs, the PIF is a forum for the premier 'and' local government in the relevant province, and the PIF is inherently and in practice, consultative and egalitarian. One of the crucial ways in which SALGA's voice can influence law and policy is that the PIF may discuss draft legislation and draft national policies relating to matters that affect provinces and/or local governments. The Premier sets the agenda, and meeting dates, but proposals for the agenda can be submitted to Premier ahead of the PIF. In practice, each province sets its own frequency of meetings, some meeting twice a year and other four times a year or as the need arises.

The District Intergovernmental Forum (DIF) is a forum for the district mayor and local mayors in his/her jurisdiction. Intergovernmental institutions such as the Budget Council (which is part of the finance MinMEC), the Budget Forum of Local Government, the National Council of Provinces and the Financial and Fiscal Commission (FFC) also bring the three spheres of government together.

Organised Local Government

South African Local Government Association (SALGA) and its provincial affiliates are recognised as organised local government and represent all 257 municipalities in the country in terms of the Organised Local Government Act.¹³³ SALGA plays a crucial role of representing local government in IGR forums.¹³⁴ However, SALGA has the difficult task of representing the interests of both urban and rural municipalities, which are often different, and are sometimes at odds with each other. Decision-making at national level in SALGA is done by SALGA's national executive, elected by the SALGA national conference. SALGA executive committee comprises of the chairperson of SALGA, 3 deputies, 6 additional members, provincial chairpersons of SALGA (ex officio), and the head of the administration (who has no vote) and optionally, three additional members. The meetings of SALGA national executive are once every three months, and when the need arises (clause 12.4.2 SALGA Constitution). The Constitution of SALGA empowers the national executive to make representations to provincial and national government (clause 12.7.5) and to determine the representation of SALGA in all national IGR structures and other national forums and such representatives have power to make decisions in these structures and forums, but they must report back to the national executive quarterly (clause 12.7.14).

At the provincial level, decision-making is done by the SALGA provincial executive committee elected by the provincial members' assembly. The SALGA provincial executive committee comprises of the Chairperson, three deputies and six additional members (it may co-opt three

¹³³ Act 52 of 1997.

¹³⁴ National Treasury: Budget Technical Forum and Winter Budget Forum; Department of Works: Technical and Political MINMEC; Department of Safety and Security: Safety and Security Technical and Political MINMEC.

additional members). Similarly, the SALGA provincial executive committee meets once every three months, and when the need arises. All municipalities in the province must be represented on the provincial executive committee. The SALGA Constitution empowers SALGA provincial executive committee to make representations to provincial government (clause 21.6.3), and to determine SALGA representation in provincial IGR structures and other forums, and such representatives have power to make decisions, but must report back to the provincial executive committee (clause 21.6.2). SALGA engages and lobbies for local government in Parliament through the portfolio committees of National Assembly (NA) (Section 163 of the Constitution). Section 163 of the Constitution enables SALGA to participate in all meetings of the National Council of Provinces (NCOP) Select Committees, NCOP plenary debates, joint sittings of NCOP and NA, NCOP Local Government Week and SALGA can designate 10 councillors to hold part-time seats in the NCOP. Although legislation does not invite SALGA into provincial legislatures, some provincial legislatures accommodate the participation of SALGA.¹³⁵ Thus SALGA gives local governments a voice in the NCOP and in some provincial legislatures.

Intergovernmental Relations Mechanisms

There are IGR mechanisms for budgeting, planning and implementation, such as implementation protocols and integrated development planning (IDP). Each municipality is required to develop an IDP in consultation with local communities, and in alignment with national and provincial strategic development plans.¹³⁶ The MFMA and the Constitution further regulate intergovernmental fiscal relations (IGFR). SALGA participates in fiscal IGR in its role as organised local government.¹³⁷

Dispute Resolution

There are mechanisms for intergovernmental dispute resolution. Section 41 requires all three spheres of government to take 'every reasonable effort' to settle disputes out of court and to use litigation only as a last resort. Furthermore, courts may refer matters back to allow alternative dispute resolution (ADR) through political processes if litigation was instituted prematurely. There are also mechanisms to resolve conflicting legislation in order to ensure coherence in the legislative framework.

¹³⁵ SALGA, 'Organised Local Government in Parliament and Provincial Legislatures' (unpublished paper 2013) 9.

¹³⁶ Secs 24 and 26 MSA 32 of 2000; Department of Provincial and Local Government, 'The Implementation of the Intergovernmental Relations Framework Act: An Inaugural Report 2005/6-2006/7' (Government of South Africa 2007) 38.

¹³⁷ Secs 9 and 10 of the MSA Act 32 of 2000; Sec 35 Public Finance Management Act 1 of 1999.

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Municipal Finance and Management Act 56 of 2003

Intergovernmental Relations Framework Act (IGRFA) 13 of 2005

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